

An anthropomorphic design of an adaptive artificial foot

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BACKGROUND

Falls remain prevalent among individuals with lower-limb loss, and uneven terrains often destabilise prosthetic users. Many adopt compensatory strategies that increase fatigue and exacerbate gait asymmetries [1], overloading the sound limb. This instability stems from the limited ground adaptability of most commercially available foot prostheses, typically composed of carbon fibre laminates, which can only offer a stiff interaction with the ground, behaving like cantilevers on irregular surfaces [2].

AIM

This work addresses the need for prosthetic feet capable of adapting to all terrains while ensuring stability through the design of a novel anthropomorphic adaptive prosthesis.

METHOD

Adaptability in current prosthetic feet is usually achieved with split toes in carbon laminates, and passive or active ankle impedance adjustments for slope navigation and swing ground clearance [2]. Our approach diverges by drawing inspiration from the human foot anatomy and functionality and exploiting soft robotics for a compliant interaction with the environment. The human foot modulates its stiffness based on gait phase and terrain, softening for ground impact absorption and stiffening for push-off propulsion [3,4]. It filters terrain irregularities: the soft tissues of the sole absorb minor roughness, while joint flexibility handles larger ones, optimizing ground contact area [4].

RESULTS

We developed the SoftFoot: an adaptive, passive, artificial foot, initially designed for robots (Figure 1) [5]. Its unique sole features five flexible chains made of modular components connected through an inextensible link and elastic bands. The intelligent design allows the sole to conform to ground profiles, while passively stretching and stiffening under load, providing stability, shock absorption, and contributing to push-off propulsion. Preliminary simulations and tests with a healthy subject using customized walking boots showed that the prosthetic SoftFoot increased the stable contact area with obstacles, leading to a mean stance load on it greater than that on a rigid foot (Figure 1) [6]. Tests with a prosthetic user indicated that the flexible sole eased obstacle negotiation while supporting body weight, reducing the user’s mental burden and compensatory movements.

Figure 1. On the left, SoftFoot prototype for robots. In the middle, comparison between the prosthetic SoftFoot and a prosthesis with a rigid sole [8]. The SoftFoot also offers a more natural aesthetic, even with footwear. On the right, sagittal force measured by a load cell placed between the foot prosthesis and the walking boot used by a healthy subject. The loading profile on obstacle (dotted line) with the SoftFoot remained closer to that for level (solid line), contrary to what occurred with the VariFlex (a carbon fiber foot by Össur), and on average larger than that of the VariFlex.

DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

The SoftFoot enhances ground adaptation, thus stability, reducing compensatory strategies and potentially fall risk. Experimental data from prosthetic user will be published to substantiate these findings (post-processing ongoing), with larger experiments planned. The passive design reduces weight, size, maintenance, and costs, thanks also to 3D-printed components. An open-source release is planned [7]. Therefore, the SoftFoot exemplifies “innovation towards sustainable rehabilitation”, providing an accessible option, especially for users in challenging environments.

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ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

This work was funded by the ERC Synergy Grant Natural BionicS (Grant Agreement No. 810346).